

k-graceful labeling for the ladder graph and the roach graph

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Abstract: A simple graph G is said to be a vertex k -graceful if there exists a vertex graceful labeling on the vertices of G . A graceful labeling of G is a vertex labeling f be an injective mapping from $V(G)$ to $[0, |E(G)| + k - 1]$ such that the edge labeling $f_e: E(G) \rightarrow [k, |E(G)| + k - 1]$ defined by $f_e(uv) = |f(u) - f(v)|$ is also injective. When $k = 1$, f is called graceful labeling, and G is called a graceful graph. There is a very famous conjecture in this area that every tree is graceful. Numerous studies have been conducted in this area over the past few decades, and several results have been obtained. In this research work, we prove that the ladder graph admits the k -graceful labeling. The ladder graph is a graph obtained from the Cartesian product of P_n and P_2 . Moreover, we studied the k -gracefulness of the roach graphs and could obtain some partial results. However, we strongly believe that every roach graph is k -graceful. Finally, we introduced two open problems for future works.

Keywords: k -graceful Labeling, Ladder graph, Roach graph

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Accepted: 13 January, 2023; **Published:** 29 January, 2023

How to cite this article: W. K. M. Indunil, D. M. T. B. Dissanayake, M. A. D. Priyadarshani, A. A. I. Perera (2023). k -graceful labeling for the ladder graph and the roach graph. *North American Academic Research*, 6(1), 116-120. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7581628>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Graceful Labeling is a famous graph labeling method and is an active research area in graph theory. This labeling method was introduced by Alexander Rosa in 1967 and was originally given the name β -labeling [1]. There are two main types of graceful labelings as vertex graceful labeling and edge graceful labeling. Over the past 50 years, many graphs have been proven to be graceful and recent work on graceful labeling includes vertex graceful labeling of ladder graphs [2]. In our work, we introduce a k -graceful labeling for ladder graphs and roach graphs $R_{2(1,n)}$ and $R_{2(2,n)}$. Applications of ladder graphs are in-network and circuit theory, and since the roach graph represents a grid structure of a ladder shape, it can be used to model a computer network structure [3]–[5]. Next, we will introduce some fundamental definitions.

Definition 1. (k -Graceful Labeling). Let $G = G(V, E)$ be a graph with $m = |E(G)|$, where $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ denote the set of vertices and edges, respectively. A graceful labeling of G is a vertex labeling $f: V \rightarrow [0, m + k - 1]$ such that f

is injective and the edge labeling $f_v: E \rightarrow [1, m + k - 1]$ defined by $f_v(uv) = |f(u) - f(v)|$ is also injective. Such a graph is called a k -graceful graph. When $k = 1$, it is called ordinary graceful labeling.

Definition 2. (The Ladder Graph). For an integer $n \geq 1$, a ladder L_n is defined by $L_n = P_n \times K_2$, where P_n is a path with n vertices and \times denotes the Cartesian product. Clearly, L_n has $2n$ vertices and $3n - 2$ edges.

Definition 3. (The Roach Graph). A roach graph is a graph with the shape of a cockroach having $2m + 2n$ vertices. It is denoted by $R_{2(m,n)}$, where $2m$ ($m \geq 1$) and $2n$ ($n \geq 2$) are the vertices in the head (antennas) and body, respectively. There are two separate paths with $m + n$ vertices and opposing m vertices in each path are joined as a ladder.

Research Methodology

Theorem 1. Every Ladder Graph is k - graceful.

Figure 1: Ladder graph $P_n \times P_2$

Proof. Let f be the vertex labeling of the ladder graph. We divide the labeling method into two parts according to the parity of n .

When n is odd:

$$f(U_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3i}{2}; & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-1 \\ k + 3n - \left(\frac{3i+5}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-2 \end{cases} \quad f(V_i) = \begin{cases} k + 3n - 3\left(\frac{i+2}{2}\right); & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-1 \\ 2 + 3\left(\frac{i-1}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-2 \end{cases}$$

When n is even:

$$f(U_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3i}{2}; & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-2 \\ k + 3n - \left(\frac{3i+5}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-1 \end{cases} \quad f(V_i) = \begin{cases} k + 3n - 3\left(\frac{i+2}{2}\right); & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-2 \\ 2 + 3\left(\frac{i-1}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-1 \end{cases}$$

We can easily check the labeling f is graceful by computing the absolute difference of each end vertices of the edges in the graph.

The idea behind this is, that we can label the $P_n \times P_2$ ladder graph gracefully from k to $(3n - 2) + (k - 1); k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

The ordinary graceful labeling can be obtained by setting $k = 1$, which a $P_n \times P_2$ ladder graph can be gracefully labeled from 1 up to $(3n - 2)$.

Next, we discuss the graceful labeling of two classes of the roach graph.

Proposition 1. $R_{2(1,n)}$ and $R_{2(2,n)}$ are graceful.

We can remove the edge $U_n V_n$ from the ladder graph L_{n+1} to construct $R_{2(1,n)}$ as in Figure 2.

Proof. Let f be the vertex labeling of the roach graph. We divide the labeling method into two parts according to the parity of n .

Figure 2: $R_{2(1,n)}$

When n is odd:

$$f(U_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3i}{2}; & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-1 \\ k + 3n - \left(\frac{3i+1}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n \end{cases} \quad f(V_i) = \begin{cases} (k-1) + 3\left(\frac{2n-i}{2}\right); & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-1 \\ 2 + 3\left(\frac{i-1}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-2 \\ f(V_{n-1}) + k; & i = n \text{ and } k = 1 \\ f(V_{n-1}) - k; & i = n \text{ and } k \neq 1 \end{cases}$$

When n is even:

$$f(U_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3i}{2}; & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n \\ k + 3n - \left(\frac{3i+1}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-1 \end{cases} \quad f(V_i) = \begin{cases} (k-1) + 3\left(\frac{2n-i}{2}\right); & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-2 \\ f(V_{n-1}) - k; & i = n \text{ and } k = 1 \\ f(V_{n-1}) + k; & i = n \text{ and } k \neq 1 \\ 2 + 3\left(\frac{i-1}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-1 \end{cases}$$

Next, we will study the gracefulness of $R_{2(2,n)}$. Let f be the vertex labeling. We can do the labeling f as follows:

Figure 3: $R_{2(2,n)}$

When n is odd:

$$f(U_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3i}{2}; & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-1 \\ 3n + \left(\frac{5-3i}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-2 \end{cases} \quad f(V_i) = \begin{cases} 3n + \left(\frac{4-3i}{2}\right); & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-1 \\ 2 + 3\left(\frac{i-1}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-2 \end{cases}$$

$$f(H_i) = \begin{cases} V_{n-1} + 1; & i = 1 \\ U_{n-1} - 2; & i = 2 \\ H_1 - 3; & i = 3 \\ H_2 + 4; & i = 4 \end{cases}$$

When n is even:

$$f(U_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3i}{2}; & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-2 \\ 3n + \left(\frac{5-3i}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-1 \end{cases} \quad f(V_i) = \begin{cases} 3n + \left(\frac{4-3i}{2}\right); & i = 0,2,4, \dots, n-2 \\ 2 + 3\left(\frac{i-1}{2}\right); & i = 1,3,5, \dots, n-1 \end{cases}$$

$$f(H_i) = \begin{cases} V_{n-1} + 1; & i = 1 \\ U_{n-1} - 2; & i = 2 \\ H_1 + 3; & i = 3 \\ H_2 - 4; & i = 4 \end{cases}$$

Results and Discussion

Now, we illustrate Theorem 1 and Proposition 1 using a couple of examples as follows,

Figure 4: 5-graceful labeling of $P_4 \times P_2$

Figure 5: 1-graceful labeling of $P_4 \times P_2$

Figure 6: 1-graceful labeling of $R_{2(1,3)}$

Figure 7: 1-graceful labeling of $R_{2(2,5)}$

Conclusion

In our research, we discussed the vertex k -graceful labeling of the ladder graphs and two classes $R_{2(1,n)}$ and $R_{2(2,n)}$ of roach graphs. We manually checked the existence of the gracefulness of some arbitrary roach graphs and verified that they are graceful. So, we strongly believe that every roach graph is graceful. Then we will introduce the following open problems:

Open Problem 01.

Every roach graph is graceful.

Open problem 02.

Every roach graph is k -graceful.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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